

Le Modèle des Aions

de 1986 - 2013 - 2021 : <http://modeledesaisons.free.fr/index.html>

NUMERICAL PARTICLES

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Preamble :

Suppose the various fields of science are islands. Then the Island of Physics could be full of vegetation. That of Mathematics would, on the contrary, be quite low. The two would seem to be connected by a long unstable footbridge on which the world would walk. Most people would take this wide road to join one another, overlooking the swamps...

Only certain rare birds could climb the unique mountain of Physics, very far from the ground, made up of eminent materials: particle physics, astrophysics, cosmology, etc ... But then wouldn't this unique mountain be rather a volcano ?

And, like buzzards, would the best seek at altitude the entrance to the famous supreme bridge directly connecting the tip of Physics to that of Mathematics, thus avoiding to take the crowded footbridge or going through the thick forest and its dangerous marshes?

But, the measure being the proof of everything, is the one who seeks and who still seeks in the right place to find since in this place a volcano reigns? Which as everyone knows does not really have a sharp top ^

Let us remember that the flame of its crater does not come from the sky but from the Earth itself. Its disastrous eruptions have also probably disjointed with the ancient kingdom of the Atlanteans as exposed on this link where we can check the triskel shape of this Atlantic island too deeply sunk on googlemaps.fr :

source : "Était-elle l'Atlantide" by Wolter SMIT
<http://fr.was-this-atlantis.info/etait-elle-atlantide.html>

So let's stay down to earth and crawl through the jungle. Let us seek this path which is so narrow and which all researchers are still struggling to find.

If it is, we will find it in fact in a place abandoned by all. And what first comes to mind is the prose of the antiques : Aristotle, just before him Plato and even more before Pythagoras and Anaxagoras for whom writing was even banned. Should I be silent ? Please note that I am only a fan who is looking for his way :

"The most limited, if adequate, is always preferable."
 Aristote (384-322 before JC)

We will now see how to explore what lane is behind the forest, through the swamps.

Introduction :

It would be too tedious to describe here the flow of ideas that allowed me to access the numerical results proposed below.

At the end of the 20th century I was able to observe that by modifying the notion of charge, this being a flow of energy moving in space-time, then it was possible to establish mathematical relations between 1 electron and proton. And this on condition therefore to modify the definition of the electric charge.

Thus a mathematical formula could connect their charges: q_e and q_p , and another allowed the relation of their volumes: V_e and V_p . These two relations then led to a mathematical relation defining the ratio β of the masses of these two particles: m_e and m_p :

$$q_p = 27 \cdot q_e \quad \text{the charge ratio which is not: } q_p = -q_e$$

$$V_e = 16 \cdot V_p \quad \text{the volume ratio}$$

$$r_e = \sqrt[3]{16} \cdot r_p \quad \text{ray ratio}$$

$$\beta = \frac{q_p^2}{q_e^2} \cdot \frac{r_e}{r_p} = 1836.1527 \quad \text{the mass ratio without units}$$

$$\beta := 27^2 \cdot \sqrt[3]{16} = 1836,96489074673 \quad \text{the mathematical ratio of masses but also the quantity of } m_e \text{ in } m_p \text{ses without units}$$

Without expanding on meta-physical considerations, it is however possible to summarize the basic principles leading to the general model of Aions:

1) There is always something smaller than what is believed to be the smallest thing and vice versa for larger things.

It is only on this condition that it is possible to describe the simple passage of time. This is the sinéqua-non condition for the existence of a space-time, and in this context it is a recomposition of the 3 spatial dimensions. In the universe we are in, time flowing from the past to the future, then the objects get smaller proportionally and all together. This looks like a Big Bang but is not because the phenomenon is seen from the inside.

2) There is continuity between all the constituent elements of space-time.

The movement of an object requires the bringing together of the elements constituting it in space and time. Even in the particular case of the EPR effect, this principle is respected because the information on the appearance of a pair passes not only through space but also through time. Thus the phenomena of spatial continuity are also immediately propagated in space without loss of distance. This is also consistent with string theories.

3) There is always a balance that governs imbalances.

The initialization of a grain of matter determines an alteration of the spatial support. If negative charges exist then in return, positive charges exert forces in opposite directions. Thus a neutral charge exists by itself being the assembly of a negative charge and another positive. It is the same for a mass which if it is created in a place necessarily gives rise to an anti-mass of equivalent energy. This principle also implies a rule of symmetry, especially for the shapes of bodies.

On the other hand, making the model consistent with the radius of the universe and even the planck length encouraged me to understand that numbers are the basis of statistics. Indeed, quantities of finite materials are assembled or disassembled according to simply mathematical rules, by operations. This is the basis of physics, without which it would not be possible to apply any scientific formula to nature.

Consequently no physical quantity can in the absolute be regarded as a constant because it is only the mathematical numbers which are constant.

We are sufficiently equipped to study particle digitization.

I. Material digitization formula :

According to the first principle explained above, the identification of an element of material provided the support for the installation of a digital scaffolding by the multiplication of the elements. We will see below that the first level brick comes from the planck constant h , its energy being completely integrated in the mass such as :

$$\begin{aligned}
 C &:= 299792458 \quad \text{en m.s}^{-1} \quad \text{the speed of light} \\
 h &:= 6,62606957 \cdot 10^{-34} \quad \text{en m}^2.\text{kg.s}^{-1} \quad \text{the planck constant} \\
 m \cdot C^2 &= h \cdot \nu \quad \text{with the unit frequency} \quad \nu = \frac{C}{\lambda} \\
 m &= h \cdot \frac{1}{\lambda} \quad \text{and with the wave length} \quad \lambda = \frac{C}{\nu} \quad \text{is} \quad \lambda = \frac{1}{\nu}
 \end{aligned}$$

Which provides the mass of a quantum such as : $m := 6,62606957 \cdot 10^{-34}$ en kg

The calculation of this re-integrated mass is a particular case of a materialized X photon, taken to its existential limit. We can calculate its characteristics. Constantly knowing that this photon is unique, I chose to name it kokkos, a term taken from the translation of the word "granule" in Greek.

$$k := 6,62606957 \cdot 10^{-34} \quad \text{en kg}$$

The mass in ev linked to this new particle is :

$$kev := 371,5939 \quad \text{en ev}$$

By applying the equation of the universe to electricity, the MDA had made it possible to highlight a mass relating to an electric charge and such that :

$$\text{avec } K \text{ telle que} \quad K := 10^{-7} \cdot C^2 = 8987551787,36818 \quad \text{Coulomb's constant}$$

$$m_v := \frac{2 \cdot K \cdot h}{C} = 3,97289136653861 \cdot 10^{-32} \quad \text{en kg}$$

see : <http://modeledesaions.free.fr/modeledesaions/modeledesaions.html>

Notice the following equality :

$$m_v := k \cdot 60 = 3,975641742 \cdot 10^{-32} \quad \text{en kg} \quad k \cdot 60 = \frac{2 \cdot K \cdot h}{C}$$

Prime numbers are indivisible numbers except by themselves. Conversely, abundant numbers are highly divisible numbers. Thus the construction of a prime number is necessarily more difficult than an abundant number. Suppose that a medium is made up of a multitude of grains of matter then the assembly of 2 grains will be easier than that of 3 and so on. However, the assembly of 5 grains will be more difficult than that of 6 grains because 5 is a prime number while 6 is built from itself but also by the operation: 2×3 .

Given the nature of time, it is possible to confuse the axis of movement of a particle with its axis of temporal evolution, since the two axes go in the same direction. In addition to the operation of the load it is necessary that this structure is hollow.

It becomes possible to envisage the assembly of 60 kokkos in the form of a hexagonal antiprism where each kokko can be lodged in a corner. Thus for a duration representing the present moment the basic structure of this particle could appear as follows :

side view of an assembly of 60 kokkos
(possibly a neutrino or an axion ?)

The linear nature of time indicates that it is possible to confuse the axis of movement of a particle with its axis of temporal evolution, since these two axes go in the same direction, here vertically.

On this principle it is possible to determine the number of operations which allow to calculate any number, in any case I succeeded in calculating them up to the number corresponding to the heaviest particles known: the Higgs boson and the quark t. Without going so far we first observe a very interesting comparison concerning the mass of the electron :

$$k \cdot 1440 = 9,5415401808 \cdot 10^{-31} \text{ en kg}$$

$$1374 \cdot k = 9,10421958918000 \cdot 10^{-31}$$

On the other hand the principle of continuity 2) obliges to keep only the numbers corresponding to this additional criterion. Thus it is only possible to build approximately cylindrical shapes and therefore in the form of ropes. The most probable association between these points is made by assembling equilateral triangles and respecting the rule of symmetry.

The general formulation of the number of points probably constituting a particle can then be deduced :

$$\text{Particule}(m; n) := m \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n i \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n i$$

For example, it is easy to write the simplified calculation formula for an electron :

$$6 \cdot (1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 = 1440 \quad \text{either in 17 alphanumeric characters !}$$

Or even that of the simplified calculation of the Higgs boson :

$$22 \cdot (1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9 = 359251200 \quad \text{either in 38 characters}$$

The list below gives the values for n from 1 to 9 and m variable from 2 to 40 in steps of 2 :

$$m := [2; 4 .. 40] \quad n := [1 .. 9]$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{for } x \in m \\ &\quad \text{for } y \in n \\ &\quad \quad P_{\frac{x}{2} y} := \text{Particule}(x; y) \end{aligned}$$

2	2	12	72	480	3600	30240	282240	2903040	32659200
4	4	24	144	960	7200	60480	564480	5806080	65318400
6	6	36	216	1440	10800	90720	846720	8709120	97977600
8	8	48	288	1920	14400	120960	1128960	11612160	130636800
10	10	60	360	2400	18000	151200	1411200	14515200	163296000
12	12	72	432	2880	21600	181440	1693440	17418240	195955200
14	14	84	504	3360	25200	211680	1975680	20321280	228614400
16	16	96	576	3840	28800	241920	2257920	23224320	261273600
18	18	108	648	4320	32400	272160	2540160	26127360	293932800
20	20	120	720	4800	36000	302400	2822400	29030400	326592000
22	22	132	792	5280	39600	332640	3104640	31933440	359251200
24	24	144	864	5760	43200	362880	3386880	34836480	391910400
26	26	156	936	6240	46800	393120	3669120	37739520	424569600
28	28	168	1008	6720	50400	423360	3951360	40642560	457228800
30	30	180	1080	7200	54000	453600	4233600	43545600	489888000
32	32	192	1152	7680	57600	483840	4515840	46448640	522547200
34	34	204	1224	8160	61200	514080	4798080	49351680	555206400
36	36	216	1296	8640	64800	544320	5080320	52254720	587865600
38	38	228	1368	9120	68400	574560	5362560	55157760	620524800
40	40	240	1440	9600	72000	604800	5644800	58060800	653184000

voir : <https://www.modeledesaions.fr/articles.php?pg=art1>

The odd m steps are not shown because they cannot relate to particles propagating in time. This phenomenon implies by the application of principle 2) that the shape of the particles is symmetrical and therefore only the even numbers m are to be taken into account.

II. Structure of digital particles :

A detailed analysis of the numerical characteristics specific to each element of the table makes it possible to demonstrate that the structure of elementary particles is based on polyhedra. They are therefore in the shape of a rope and with a polygonal base. n represents the number of layers or thickness of the particle and m gives the starting layer of thickness.

The most emblematic of all known particles is certainly the electron since it serves as the basis of all electricity. We can now make a more precise representation :

digital electron
top view

digital electron
3/4 view

This table contains almost all the known particles but to be able to identify them by measurement it is necessary to have postulated at the outset that there is a deformation of the pure calculus. This transformation is simply due to Relativity as a consequence of the displacement of the Universe or what amounts to the same to its depolarization dv :

if the mass of the electron is 0.511 Mev

$$dv := \frac{0,511}{1440} = 0,000354861$$

$m =$	$P \cdot dv =$	2	0,00071	0,00426	0,02555	0,17033	1,2775	10,731	100,156	1030,176	11589,48
		4	0,00142	0,00852	0,0511	0,34067	2,555	21,462	200,312	2060,352	23178,96
		6	0,00213	0,01278	0,07665	0,511	3,8325	32,193	300,468	3090,528	34768,44
		8	0,00284	0,01703	0,1022	0,68133	5,11	42,924	400,624	4120,704	46357,92
		10	0,00355	0,02129	0,12775	0,85167	6,3875	53,655	500,78	5150,88	57947,4
		12	0,00426	0,02555	0,1533	1,022	7,665	64,386	600,936	6181,056	69536,88
		14	0,00497	0,02981	0,17885	1,19233	8,9425	75,117	701,092	7211,232	81126,36
		16	0,00568	0,03407	0,2044	1,36267	10,22	85,848	801,248	8241,408	92715,84
		18	0,00639	0,03832	0,22995	1,533	11,4975	96,579	901,404	9271,584	104305,32
		20	0,0071	0,04258	0,2555	1,70333	12,775	107,31	1001,56	10301,76	115894,8
		22	0,00781	0,04684	0,28105	1,87367	14,0525	118,041	1101,716	11331,936	127484,28
		24	0,00852	0,0511	0,3066	2,044	15,33	128,772	1201,872	12362,112	139073,76
		26	0,00923	0,05536	0,33215	2,21433	16,6075	139,503	1302,028	13392,288	150663,24
		28	0,00994	0,05962	0,3577	2,38467	17,885	150,234	1402,184	14422,464	162252,72
		30	0,01065	0,06388	0,38325	2,555	19,1625	160,965	1502,34	15452,64	173842,2
		32	0,01136	0,06813	0,4088	2,72533	20,44	171,696	1602,496	16482,816	185431,68
		34	0,01207	0,07239	0,43435	2,89567	21,7175	182,427	1702,652	17512,992	197021,16
		36	0,01278	0,07665	0,4599	3,066	22,995	193,158	1802,808	18543,168	208610,64
		38	0,01348	0,08091	0,48545	3,23633	24,2725	203,889	1902,964	19573,344	220200,12
		40	0,01419	0,08517	0,511	3,40667	25,55	214,62	2003,12	20603,52	231789,6

Yes but which basic unit is it? Well it is simply the Planck quantum k or $kokko$ which determines the unit mass. So the calculation of the mass of the electron in kg is :

$$k := 6,62606957 \cdot 10^{-34} \quad \text{is the mass of the Planck quantum in kg}$$

$$masse_electron := Particule(6; 4) \cdot k = 9,541540181 \cdot 10^{-31} \quad \text{kg}$$

Similarly for the Higgs boson we find the mass :

$$masse_boson_Higgs := Particule(22; 9) \cdot k = 2,380423444 \cdot 10^{-25} \quad \text{kg}$$

We can thus identify the following particles by their number of kokkos :

n = 3	$neutrino := Particule(4; 3) = 144$	(there are different identifications for neutrinos)
n = 4	$electron := Particule(6; 4) = 1440$	$1440 \cdot \frac{3}{\pi} = 1375,0987$
	$positon := Particule(18; 4) = 4320$	
n = 6	$muon := Particule(20; 6) = 302400$	$\frac{muon}{electron} = 210$
	$anti_muon := Particule(28; 6) = 423360$	

The Millennium article "Towards Science Unification Through Number Theory" by F. M. Sanchez, M. H. Grosman, R. Veysseyre, H. Veysseyre, D. Weige also mentions this exact value of 210 in its introduction :

This article shows, more fundamentally, the symmetry between the four basic primes: 2; 3; 5; 7, considered as the cosmic computation bases. Indeed, the symmetric combinations $2 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7 = 210$ and $(2+3+5+7)(2 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7) = 3570$ give the brute mass ratios, relative to electron, of the Muon and Tau.

However, the mass ratio with the tauon is not quite the same :

n = 7	$quark_anti_u := Particule(2; 7) = 282240$	
	$quark_d := Particule(4; 7) = 564480$	
	$quark_anti_d := Particule(6; 7) = 846720$	
	$quark_u := Particule(10; 7) = 1411200$	
	$quark_anti_c := Particule(32; 7) = 4515840$	
	$tauon := Particule(36; 7) = 5080320$	$\frac{tauon}{electron} = 3528 \quad (/3570)$
n = 9	$boson_W := Particule(14; 9) = 228614400$	
	$boson_Z := Particule(16; 9) = 261273600$	
	$boson_Higgs := Particule(22; 9) = 359251200$	
	$boson_Higgs_2 := Particule(24; 9) = 391910400$	(existence not yet confirmed)
	$quark_t := Particule(30; 9) = 489888000$	

We can now identify the nucleons which are composed of quarks :

$$proton := quark_u \cdot 2 + quark_d = 3387000 \quad neutron := quark_u + quark_d \cdot 2 = 2540000$$

$$\frac{proton}{electron} = 2352 \quad (/1836) \quad \frac{neutron}{electron} = 1764$$

By looking for the number of real kokkos in the real masses of these nucleons, we calculate :

$$\frac{1,6726 \cdot 10^{-27}}{h} = 2524271,7154 \quad \text{for proton}$$

$$\frac{1,674 \cdot 10^{-27}}{h} = 2526384,5819 \quad \text{for neutron}$$

The ratio of these two nucleons with the electron will give the raw numbers :

$\frac{proton}{electron} = 2352$	mais dans le monde réel on trouve :	$\frac{1,6726 \cdot 10^{-27}}{9,1094 \cdot 10^{-31}} = 1836,1253$
$\frac{neutron}{electron} = 1764$	mais dans le monde réel on trouve :	$\frac{1,674 \cdot 10^{-27}}{9,1094 \cdot 10^{-31}} = 1837,6622$

The following table gives the masses in kg. These masses are of course a first approach to the real masses since it is then necessary to apply different adjustments having for their origin distinct physical phenomena: the number of points per revolution (Archimedes' formula, parameter specific to each particle), the deformation of our universe compared to the perfect universe of reference, the parameters applicable to all the particles, etc ... :

$P \cdot k =$	$1,33 \cdot 10^{-33}$	$7,95 \cdot 10^{-33}$	$4,77 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$3,18 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$2,39 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$1,87 \cdot 10^{-28}$
	$2,65 \cdot 10^{-33}$	$1,59 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$9,54 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$6,36 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$4,77 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$4,01 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$3,74 \cdot 10^{-28}$
	$3,98 \cdot 10^{-33}$	$2,39 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$1,43 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$9,54 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$7,16 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$6,01 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$5,61 \cdot 10^{-28}$
	$5,3 \cdot 10^{-33}$	$3,18 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$1,91 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$1,27 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$9,54 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$8,01 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$7,48 \cdot 10^{-28}$
	$6,63 \cdot 10^{-33}$	$3,98 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$2,39 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$1,59 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$1,19 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$9,35 \cdot 10^{-28}$
	$7,95 \cdot 10^{-33}$	$4,77 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$2,86 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$1,91 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$1,43 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$1,2 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$1,12 \cdot 10^{-27}$
	$9,28 \cdot 10^{-33}$	$5,57 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$3,34 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$2,23 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$1,67 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$1,4 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$1,31 \cdot 10^{-27}$
	$1,06 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$6,36 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$3,82 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$2,54 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$1,91 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$1,6 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$1,5 \cdot 10^{-27}$...
	$1,19 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$7,16 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$4,29 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$2,86 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$2,15 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$1,8 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$1,68 \cdot 10^{-27}$
	$1,33 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$7,95 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$4,77 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$3,18 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$2,39 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$1,87 \cdot 10^{-27}$
	$1,46 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$8,75 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$5,25 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$3,5 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$2,62 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$2,2 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$2,06 \cdot 10^{-27}$
	$1,59 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$9,54 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$5,72 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$3,82 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$2,86 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$2,4 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$2,24 \cdot 10^{-27}$
	$1,72 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$1,03 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$6,2 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$4,13 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$3,1 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$2,6 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$2,43 \cdot 10^{-27}$
	$1,86 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$1,11 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$6,68 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$4,45 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$3,34 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$2,81 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$2,62 \cdot 10^{-27}$
	$1,99 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$1,19 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$7,16 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$4,77 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$3,58 \cdot 10^{-29}$	$3,01 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$2,81 \cdot 10^{-27}$

The positions of the quarks are very probable even if some are missing because the distinction between mass energy and electric energy is not yet well defined at the present time.

Certain particles are in the process of being identified, in particular boson_u which makes the link during the creation of an electron-positron pair from gamma photons, hence probably :

$$boson_u := Particule(24; 4) = 5760 \quad photon_gamma := Particule(12; 4) = 2880$$

$$\gamma \Rightarrow e^- + e^+ \\ 24 + 48 = 72$$

The drawing below gives the mechanism of assembly and disassembly of the particles by toothed wheel on anti-prisms with polygonal bases. For example, it is easy to write the simplified calculation formula for an electron :

voir : https://woodgears.ca/gear_cutting/template_fr.html

Depending on whether the particles turn in one direction or the other, the sign of the quantum spin number is reversed. e the simplified calculation formula of an electron:

III. Probability of materialization :

The probability of these particles appearing is therefore a function of the abundance of the number linked. I ran my programs for a good year to perform a calculation giving the number of operations for each figure up to 110 million and also around those of the largest P. The matiere.csv file also contains the values of the probabilities for the numbers in the table of operations :

```
file := importData("C:\matiere.csv")
s := [1..441]
for z ∈ s
  if file_z 2 < 41
    P
    file_z 2 file_z 1 := file_z 3
    Probabilité
    file_z 2 file_z 1 := file_z 4
  else
    0
```

This also makes it possible to calculate a probability of materialization such as :

$$\text{Probabilité} = \frac{P-1}{P}$$

2	0	0,25	0,20833	0,13125	0,07444	0,05661	0,02397	0,01805
4	0,25	0,25	0,19444	0,10833	0,06708	0,05089	0,01997	0,0141
6	0,16667	0,22222	0,13889	0,11806	0,05602	0,04056	0,0208	0,01292
8	0,25	0,22917	0,15972	0,08542	0,05847	0,04371	0,01614	0,01081
10	0,1	0,16667	0,14167	0,07083	0,03361	0,03579	0,01608	0,01325
12	0,25	0,20833	0,12963	0,1	0,05222	0,03723	0,01768	0,01022
14	0,07143	0,11905	0,10119	0,07411	0,0456	0,02557	0,00892	0,00947
16	0,25	0,1875	0,13194	0,06589	0,04847	0,03631	0,01273	0,00814
18	0,16667	0,13889	0,08642	0,08819	0,03883	0,02674	0,01605	0,00866
20	0,15	0,16667	0,13472	0,06	0,03133	0,03307	0,01371	0,01054
22	0,04545	0,07576	0,06439	0,04716	0,02902	0,02558	0,01166	0,00983
24	0,25	0,19444	0,11111	0,0809	0,04657	0,0326	0,01456	0,00793
26	0,03846	0,0641	0,05449	0,0399	0,02455	0,02165	0,00986	0,00832
28	0,10714	0,11905	0,09623	0,06324	0,04321	0,02362	0,00758	0,00753
30	0,13333	0,13889	0,1	0,06708	0,02644	0,02655	0,01452	0,00977
32	0,1875	0,15104	0,10156	0,04948	0,03922	0,02928	0,00982	0,00604
34	0,02941	0,04902	0,04167	0,03051	0,01877	0,01655	0,00754	0,00636
36	0,22222	0,13889	0,08333	0,0765	0,03702	0,02501	0,01388	0,00694
38	0,02632	0,04386	0,03728	0,0273	0,0168	0,01481	0,00675	0,00569
40	0,15	0,15417	0,11806	0,04854	0,02794	0,02913	0,01131	0,00822

see : <https://www.modeledesaisons.fr/articles.php?pg=art1>

The table below can be a first approach, provided that the elementary particles are separated from the particles composed of several elementary particles :

```
zoom := 100
for i ∈ m/2
  Proba_3_i 1 := i
  Proba_3_i 2 := Probabilité_i 3 · zoom
  Proba_4_i 1 := i
  Proba_4_i 2 := Probabilité_i 4 · zoom
  Proba_6_i 1 := i
  Proba_6_i 2 := Probabilité_i 6 · zoom
  Proba_7_i 1 := i
  Proba_7_i 2 := Probabilité_i 7 · zoom
```


{ Proba_3
 { Proba_4
 { Proba_6
 { Proba_7

This graph can be compared to the particle stability curve assumed by physicist R.L. Vallée from resonances in diffuse energy :

see page 38 : <http://benjamin.lisan.free.fr/jardin.secret/EcritsScientifiques/pseudo-sciences/TheorieSynergetique.pdf>

n = 3 et o = 12 vt ?

n = 4 et o = 60

$m =$	2	$Dents(m; 3; 12) =$	6	anti_νμ ?	$Dents(m; 4; 60) =$	8	e-	
	4		12			16		
	6		18			24		
	8		24			32		
	10		30			40		
	12		36	anti_νμ ?		48		photon γ
	14		42			56		
	16		48			64		
	18		54			72		e+
	20		60			80		
	22		66			88		
	24		72	νμ ?		96		photon γ
	26		78			104		
	28		84			112		
	30		90			120		
	32		96			128		
	34		102			136		
	36		108			144		
	38		114			152		
	40		120			160		
42	126		168					
44	132		176					
46	138		184					
48	144	vt	192					
50	150		200					

n = 5 et o = 350

n = 6 et o = 2520

$m =$	2	$Dents(m; 5; 360) =$	10	$Dents(m; 6; 2520) =$	12	μ- ?	
	4		20		24		
	6		30		36		
	8		40		48		
	10		50		60		
	12		60		72		
	14		70		84		
	16		80		96		
	18		90		108		
	20		100		120		μ+ ?
	22		110		132		
	24		120		144		
	26		130		156		
	28		140		168		
	30		150		180		
	32		160		192		
	34		170		204		
	36		180		216		
	38		190		228		
	40		200		240		
42	210	252					
44	220	264					
46	230	276					
48	240	288					
50	250	300					

We notice neutral points on key m halfway between a particle and are anti-particle: 12, 24, for the electron. This is certainly due to the symmetry of the loads.

		n = 7 et o = 20160		n = 8 et o = 81440	
$m =$	2	$Dents(m; 7; 20160) =$	14	anti_u	16
	4		28	d	32
	6		42		48
	8		56	anti_d	64
	10		70	u	80
	12		84		96
	14		98		112
	16		112	s ?	128
	18		126		144
	20		140		160
	22		154		176
	24		168		192
	26		182		208
	28		196		224
	30		210		240
	32		224	anti_c ?	256
	34		238		272
	36		252	tau+ ?	288
	38		266		304
	40		280	c ? oddéron ?	320
	42		294		336
	44		308		352
⋮	⋮		⋮		
		n = 9 et o = 1814400		n = 10 et o = 19958400	
$m =$	2	$Dents(m; 9; 1814400) =$	18	anti_t ?	20
	4		36		40
	6		54		60
	8		72		80
	10		90		100
	12		108	anti_b ?	120
	14		126	W+-	140
	16		144	Z°	160
	18		162		180
	20		180	H°	200
	22		198		220
	24		216		240
	26		234		260
	28		252		280
	30		270	t	300
	32		288		320
	34		306		340
	36		324		360
	38		342		380
	40		360		400
	⋮		⋮		⋮

By noting that the $n = 2$, $n = 5$ and $n = 8$ do not seem to be fulfilled, is it possible to deduce from this that these n are elements of the logical sequence listing the sum of the prime numbers taken two by two? Indeed this list being: 2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, ... Then it would follow that :

$$2 = 3-1 = 5-3 ; 5 = 2+3 ; 8 = 3+5 ; 12 = 5+7 ; 18 = 7+11 ; 24 = 11+13 \dots \quad \text{OEIS A001043}$$

Or even this series of 3 figures could just as easily evoke the following triangular series :

$$a(n) := 3 \cdot n + 2 \quad a(0) = 2 \quad a(1) = 5 \quad a(2) = 8 \quad a(3) = 11 \quad a(4) = 14$$

see : <https://www.mathway.com/popular-problems/Precalculus/412312> et OEIS A016789

To decide between these 2 suites, the LHC would have to be able to detect enormous masses, which is impossible to date, without having a good logical reason for doing so ...

V. Cascade of decays :

==> Les baryons (made up of 3 quarks) :

The nucléons :

The protons :

$$p^+ = \begin{matrix} u & + & u & + & d \\ 70 & + & 70 & + & 28 \end{matrix} = 168$$

$$anti_p = \begin{matrix} anti_u & + & anti_u & + & anti_d \\ 14 & + & 14 & + & 28 \end{matrix} = 84$$

$$p^+ + anti_p = \begin{matrix} u & + & u & + & d & + & 84 \\ ? & 70 & + & 70 & + & 28 & = & 168 \end{matrix} \quad \text{mais} \quad p^+ + anti_p = 252 \Rightarrow \begin{matrix} t & + & anti_t \\ 270 & + & 18 & ? \end{matrix}$$

The neutrons :

$$n^0 = \begin{matrix} u & + & d & + & d \\ 70 & + & 28 & + & 28 \end{matrix} = 126$$

$$n^0 = 126 \Rightarrow \begin{matrix} w^- & + & ? \\ 126 & & \end{matrix}$$

$$n^0 = 126 \Rightarrow \begin{matrix} p^+ & - & e^- & - & anti_ve \\ u & + & d & + & u & - & e^- & - & anti_ve & = & 126 \\ en\ 880\ s & 70 & + & 28 & + & 70 & - & 24 & - & 18 & = & 126 \end{matrix}$$

Quark t :

$$t = 270 \Rightarrow \begin{matrix} b & + & w^+ & + & ? \\ 448 & + & 126 & \Rightarrow & 574 - 270 = 104\ \text{ou}\ -104\ ? \end{matrix}$$

$$quark_b := Particule(64; 7) = 9031680$$

$$Dents(64; 7; 20160) = 448$$

$$t^- = 270 \Rightarrow \begin{matrix} w^- & + & vt \\ 126 & + & 144\ ? \end{matrix}$$

$$anti_t = 234 \Rightarrow \begin{matrix} w^- & + & anti_b \\ 126 & + & 108\ ? \end{matrix}$$

The hyperons :

Lambda :

$$\Lambda^0 = 210 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cccc} u & + & d & + & s & + & \gamma \\ 70 & + & 28 & + & 112 & + & 0 \text{ ?} \\ p^+ & + & d & + & \text{anti}_v & & \\ 168 & + & 28 & + & 14 \text{ ?} & & \end{array}$$

$$\Lambda^0 = 210 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} n^0 & + & \Pi^0 \\ 126 & + & 84 \end{array} \quad \text{ou}$$

$$\Lambda^0 = 210 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} p^+ & + & \Pi^- \\ 168 & + & 42 \end{array}$$

Sigma :

$$\Sigma^- = 168 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} n^0 & + & \Pi^- \\ 126 & + & 42 \end{array}$$

$$\Sigma^0 = 210 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} \Lambda^0 & + & \gamma \\ 210 & + & 0 \end{array} \quad \text{ou}$$

$$\Sigma^0 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cccc} u & + & d & + & s \\ 70 & + & 28 & + & 112 = 210 \end{array}$$

$$\Sigma^+ = 252 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} n^0 & + & \Pi^+ \\ 126 & + & 126 \end{array} \quad \text{ou}$$

$$\Sigma^+ = 252 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} p^+ & + & \Pi^0 \\ 168 & + & 84 \end{array}$$

$$\Sigma^+ b = 588 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} u & + & u & + & b \\ 70 & + & 70 & + & 448 \end{array} \quad \text{ou}$$

$$\Sigma^+ b = 588 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} \Lambda^0 b & + & \Pi^+ \\ 546 & + & 126 = 672 \\ \implies & & 84 = \Pi^0 \end{array}$$

$$\Sigma^- b = 504 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} d & + & d & + & b \\ 28 & + & 28 & + & 448 \end{array} \quad \text{ou}$$

$$\Sigma^- b = 504 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} \Lambda^0 b & + & \Pi^+ \\ 546 & - & 42 = 504 \\ \implies & & ? \end{array}$$

Ksi :

$$\Xi^0 = 294 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} u & + & s & + & s \\ 70 & + & 112 & + & 112 \end{array} \quad \text{ou}$$

$$\Xi^0 = 294 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} \Lambda^0 & + & \Pi^- \\ 210 & + & 84 \end{array}$$

$$\Xi^- = 252 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} d & + & s & + & s \\ 28 & + & 112 & + & 112 \end{array} \quad \text{ou}$$

$$\Xi^- = 252 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} \Lambda^0 & + & \Pi^- \\ 210 & + & 42 \end{array}$$

$$\Xi^- b = 630 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} d & + & s & + & b \\ 28 & + & 112 & + & 448 \end{array}$$

Omega :

$$\Omega^- = 336 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} s & + & s & + & s \\ 112 & + & 112 & + & 112 \end{array} \quad \text{ou}$$

$$\Omega^- = 336 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} \Xi^0 & + & \Pi^- \\ 294 & + & 42 \end{array}$$

$$\Omega^- = 336 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} \Lambda^0 & + & K^- \\ 210 & + & 126 \end{array} \quad \text{ou}$$

$$\Omega^- = 336 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} \Xi^0 & + & \Pi^- \\ 294 & + & 42 \end{array}$$

$$\Omega^- = 336 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} \Xi^- & + & \Pi^0 \\ 252 & + & 84 \end{array}$$

$$\Omega^- b = 672 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} \Omega^- & + & \Psi \\ 336 & + & 336 \\ \Omega^- & + & c & + & \text{anti}_c \\ 336 & + & 280 & + & 56 \end{array}$$

$$\Omega^0 b = 630 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} \Xi^- & + & \Pi^+ & + & ? \\ 588 & + & 126 & - & 84 = d + \text{anti}_d = \Pi^0 \end{array}$$

$$\Omega^0 c = 504 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} s & + & s & + & c \\ 112 & + & 112 & + & 280 \end{array} \quad \text{ou}$$

$$\Omega^0 c = 504 \Rightarrow \begin{array}{cccc} \Omega^- & + & \Pi^+ & + & ? \\ 336 & + & 126 & & \\ \Omega^- & + & u & + & \text{anti}_d \\ 336 & + & 70 & + & 56 & + & ? \end{array}$$

==> The mésons (made up of 2 quarks) :

The kaons :

$$\begin{aligned}
 K^+ &= u + \text{anti}_s \Rightarrow u + w^+ + \text{gluon} + \text{anti}_u \\
 294 &= 70 + 224 \Rightarrow 70 + 126 + 84 + 14 \\
 &\Rightarrow u + \text{anti}_d + u + \text{anti}_d + d + \text{anti}_u \\
 &\Rightarrow 70 + 56 + 70 + 56 + 28 + 14 \\
 &\text{soit : } 70 + 56 + 70 + 56 + 28 + 14 = 294
 \end{aligned}$$

$$K^- = 126 \Rightarrow \text{anti}_u + s$$

$$14 + 112$$

The pions :

$$\Pi^+ = 126 \Rightarrow u + \text{anti}_d \quad \text{ou} \quad \Pi^+ = 126 \Rightarrow \mu^+ + \nu_\mu$$

$$70 + 56 \quad \quad \quad 168 + -42 ?$$

$$\Pi^0 = 84 \Rightarrow d + \text{anti}_d \quad \text{ou} \quad \Pi^0 = 84 \Rightarrow u + \text{anti}_u$$

$$28 + 56 \quad \quad \quad 70 + 14$$

$$\Pi^- = 42 \Rightarrow \text{anti}_u + d \quad \text{ou} \quad \Pi^- = 42 \Rightarrow \mu^- + \text{anti}_\nu_\mu$$

$$14 + 28 \quad \quad \quad 120 ? + -78 ?$$

$$\text{ou} \quad \Pi^- = 42 \Rightarrow e^- + \text{anti}_\nu_e$$

$$24 + 18$$

omega :

$$w^+ \Rightarrow u + d + s$$

$$70 + 28 + ? = 126 ?$$

$$w^- \Rightarrow e^- + \text{anti}_\nu_e$$

$$24 + 18 = 126 ?$$

psi :

$$\Psi \Rightarrow c + \text{anti}_c$$

$$280 + 56 ?$$

The muons :

$$\mu^+ = 168 \Rightarrow e^+ + \nu_e + \text{anti}_\nu_\mu$$

$$72 + 96 = 54 ? + 42 ?$$

$$\mu^- = 120 \Rightarrow e^- + \text{anti}_\nu_e + \nu_\mu \quad \mu^- = 120 \Rightarrow w^- + \nu_\mu$$

$$24 + 96 = 18 + 78 ? \quad \quad \quad 126 + -6 ?$$

$$\mu^- = 120 \Rightarrow e^- + e^+ + e^- \Rightarrow e^- + \gamma + \gamma - \nu_e ?$$

$$24 + 72 + 24 \quad \quad \quad 6 ?$$

taupon :

$$\text{tau}^+ \Rightarrow \mu^+ + \nu_\mu + \text{anti}_\nu_\tau \quad \text{ou} \quad \text{tau}^+ \Rightarrow e^+ + \nu_e + \text{anti}_\nu_\tau$$

$$168 + 78 + 6 ? = 252 ? \quad \quad \quad 72 + ? + 6 ? = 252 ?$$

On the other hand we can easily calculate the thickness of an element of an elementary particle by distinguishing the first term of the formula, namely :

$$Epaisseur(m; n) := m \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n i$$

The result therefore provides the number of Kokkos constituting a particle disc. Inevitably the other part of the formula must be the length of the particle.

$$Particule := Epaisseur \cdot Longueur$$

VI. Particle length :

Without going so far as to imagine complicated and almost impossible solutions, it is immediately possible to determine the size of elementary particles by dividing the total number of Kokkos divided by the number of a layer of teeth. Is :

$$\text{Longueur}(n) := \prod_{i=1}^n i$$

Or more simply:

$$\text{Longueur}(n) := n !$$

So for each n of the series we will find the series of factorials 1! 2! 3! 4! 5! 6! 7! ... :

$1 = 1$	$\text{Longueur}(1) = 1$	
$1 \cdot 2 = 2$	$\text{Longueur}(2) = 2$	
$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 = 6$	$\text{Longueur}(3) = 6$	
$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 = 24$	$\text{Longueur}(4) = 24$	for electron series
$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 = 120$	$\text{Longueur}(5) = 120$	
$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 = 720$	$\text{Longueur}(6) = 720$	
$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 = 5040$	$\text{Longueur}(7) = 5040$	or the main quarks
$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 = 40320$	$\text{Longueur}(8) = 40320$	
$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9 = 362880$	$\text{Longueur}(9) = 362880$	
$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9 \cdot 10 = 3628800$	$\text{Longueur}(10) = 3628800$	

The result of the previous value is multiplied by the index hence the following: 1 by 2, 2, by 3, 6, by 4, 24, by 5, 120, by 6, 720, by 7, 5040, by 8, 40320, par 9, 362880, par 10, 3628800 ... This gives the number of layers n times thinner in order to suit the duration and length of the limit instant, a consequence of the casimir effect.

But it is also possible to relate it to the series of calculation of the number of teeth by :

$\text{Dents}(1; 1; 1) = 1$	
$\text{Dents}(1; 2; 3) = 2$	
$\text{Dents}(2; 3; 12) = 6$	
$\text{Dents}(6; 4; 60) = 24$	for electron series
$\text{Dents}(24; 5; 360) = 120$	
$\text{Dents}(120; 6; 2520) = 720$	
$\text{Dents}(720; 7; 20160) = 5040$	or the main quarks
$\text{Dents}(5040; 8; 181440) = 40320$	
$\text{Dents}(40320; 9; 1814400) = 362880$	
$\text{Dents}(362880; 10; 19958400) = 3628800$	

We then observe that the electron is as long as it has teeth, which indicates that it can roll on itself, which is certainly a guarantee of stability.

So for each n of the series we will find the complementary OEIS A010796 series :

$$a(n) := n! \cdot \frac{(n+1)!}{2} \quad \text{is} \quad n! * A001710 = A010796$$

$1 \cdot 1 = 1$	$a(1) = 1$
$2 \cdot 3 = 6$	$a(2) = 6$
$6 \cdot 12 = 72$	$a(3) = 72$
$24 \cdot 60 = 1440$	$a(4) = 1440$
$120 \cdot 360 = 43200$	$a(5) = 43200$
$720 \cdot 2520 = 1814400$	$a(6) = 1814400$
$5040 \cdot 20160 = 101606400$	$a(7) = 101606400$
$40320 \cdot 181440 = 7315660800$	$a(8) = 7315660800$
$362880 \cdot 1814400 = 658409472000$	$a(9) = 658409472000$
$3628800 \cdot 19958400 = 72425041920000$	$a(10) = 72425041920000$

So for each n of this new series, the OEIS A010796, it is probable to find stable mathematical values. So on, it must be possible to deduce new series as you go and to put them in correspondence with real particles already known in order to reveal specific properties for each number.

The notion of particle spin is easy to integrate because it is simply the direction in which the cylinders turn. On the other hand, those of gluon strangeness beauty color charm must necessarily correspond to parameters more related to each particle.

Certain particles are encountered several times in the table, which seems to indicate that they can appear in several structures unless they are distinct particles. It all depends on the definition we want to give to an elementary particle and also on the reactions in which they occur.

On the contrary, others seem not to correspond with the identification of particles exposed today by the scientific community and therefore certainly remain "to be discovered" ! This makes purely mathematical relationships a powerful research tool.

It is also likely that some others have a negative characteristic number, which could present a link to an inverse parallel world made up of negative masses. This could probably be observed through neutrinos and their anti-particles.

Conclusion

The work presented in this document is the result of a long reflection based on a graphic analysis because I have always sought to understand things concretely. This certainly because I am only an amateur. Thus it is greatly possible to improve these results by deepening what is accessible to the professional world of research today.

However my isolation from the official scientific world will have allowed me to have an original view allowing me perhaps to assume more simply the current errors. In particular the Big-Bang, Relativity, the notions of elementary charge must be greatly redefined, but not only.

As a reminder, the subjects below that I had to admit in order to establish this research:

- Relativity needs to be reviewed from a theoretical point of view for several reasons
- the Big-Bang does not exist as such because it is only time that passes
- the concept of charge needs to be reviewed from several points of view
- the materialization is digital at the base which makes the universe calculating

Many characteristic numbers of particles could not be found in this study and it must be possible for specialists to fill in all the missing boxes. The experts have, now that the path through the swamps is found, it seems to me a lot to do to finally build their big bridge !

On the other hand, it is necessary to highlight parallel worlds. Indeed there are undoubtedly close links between juxtaposed universes based on mathematical formulations remaining to be specified because of quantum nature. As a consequence of which there must then, just as logically, exist mathematical formulations within our own real world, certainly more complex, and which remain to be discovered.

The whole set out above has only been possible if we pose a new model of how physics works. In fact in return it is also a piece of evidence implying that the Aions model has succeeded in approaching the ultimate truth.

The following diagram summarizes the perfect world versus the real world which is likely to take the form of an egg :

The theory of the cosmic egg see : <http://www.writingbox.net/oeufcosmique/menu.htm>

The passage from a spherical shape to an ovoid shape can only be done if we consider that the entire Universe is animated by a cosmic speed which places it in motion in a fixed frame of reference:

*"Give me a fixed point and a lever and I will lift the Earth."
Archimède (287 à 212 before JC)*

Finally, the beta formula cited at the beginning of the document is a counter-example of a numerical value in the real world which turns into non-mathematical in the perfect world :

$$\beta := 27^2 \cdot \sqrt[3]{16} = 1836,9649$$

$$\frac{\text{proton}}{\text{électron}} = 2352$$

$$\frac{\text{neutron}}{\text{électron}} = 1764$$

These results on volume and charge are therefore certainly not mathematical in the Perfect world, but tend to be mathematical in the real world.